

A UNIQUE COLLECTION OF LITERARY WORKS OFTEN CONFUSED (PART-I)

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ABSTRACT

After reading British, Indian , American & some Commonwealth literature, I found huge works scattered here and there in various books which sometimes confuses the readers/competitors in the examination hall due to the inherent similarities in these titled works. To avoid this type of common confusion, I planned to search and arrange the important works first , their similarity wise and their frequency wise and then I compiled an exhaustive list of these selected works to facilitate the learners to make clear cut distinction among the various titles of the literary works. My research paper is based on the principles of effective teaching-learning and effective memorisation. My reaserch paper is also entertaining since it enhances the concept of - Learning is Fun.This is my attempt in the pedagogy of teaching-learning of english literature. I hope my collection will help the students as well as teachers who can frame confusing Multiple Choice Questions (M.C.Q) to refine their learning and also to check the depth of students' learning. About 750 works are included in this research paper and these works are not the last but the least. This research paper will be more useful to those who have read at least once The History of English Literature. It will make the readers to realise similar titles of the literary works as dissimilar and vice-versa. . I have divided my research paper in two parts, as Part-I & Part-II

Major Keywords: *Principles, Essays ,Complaint, Fall, Confessions, Fortunes, Triumph, Little, Children, Sister, Mr./Mrs., Son, Father, Husband, Wife, Man, Woman, Lady, Portraits ,Margaret, Melancholy, Song, Honour, Roots, Mountains, Coming, View/Vision, Prometheus, Death, Art, Lord, Hymn, Masque, Box, Troylus & Crysede ,Glass , Goodbye etc...*

INTRODUCTION:

My research paper covers the literary works from British, American, Indian & Commonwealth literature which readers often confuses. As we knew very well that there are three levels of learning viz. Memory level, Understanding level & Reflective level of learning. Usually readers used to memorise the literary works that is essential but this memorisation must be supplemented with proper understanding .That's why , my research paper is associated with higher levels of learning i.e. Understanding & Reflective Levels of

learning. I have tried my best in sequencing the selected literary works which readers often confuses. I strived hard to give a sort of continuity to my collection so that the readers may easily associate the various works of this collection in their mind. I have divided my research paper in two parts, as Part-I & Part-II. I am quite sure that after reading the both parts of this paper , readers will be able to differentiate & integrate the often confused literary works in an entertaining way. About 750 literary works are included in this research paper (Part-I) which are given below with their keywords highlighted in the italics.

✚	Essays on the <i>Principles</i> of Human Action	- William Hazlitt
✚	The <i>Principles</i> of Human Knowledge	- George Barkeley
✚	The <i>Principles</i> of Water	- Jon Silkin
✚	<i>Principia</i> Mathematica	- Bertrand Russell & A. N. Whitehead
✚	<i>Principia</i>	- Sir Isaac Newton
✚	<i>Principles</i> of Sociology	- Herbert Spencer
✚	<i>Principles</i> of Social Reconstruction	- Bertrand Russell
✚	The <i>Principles</i> of Literary Criticism	- I. A. Richards
✚	<i>Principles</i> of Biology	- Herbert Spencer
✚	<i>Principles</i> of Geology	- Lyell
✚	<i>Principles</i> of Psychology	- William James
✚	New <i>Principles</i> of Psychology	- Herbert Spencer
✚	<i>Principles</i> of Ethics	- Herbert Spencer
✚	<i>Laws</i> of Higher Life	- Annie Besant
✚	<i>Essays</i> of Elia	- Charles Lamb
✚	<i>Essay</i> on Man	- A. Pope
✚	<i>Essays</i> in Criticism	- Matthew Arnold
✚	An <i>Essay</i> on Criticism	- Alexander Pope
✚	<i>Essays</i> on Gita	- Aurobindo Ghosh
✚	<i>Essays</i> on Life	- Samuel Butler
✚	An <i>Essay</i> on <i>Man/ Mind</i>	- Elizabeth Barrett Browning
✚	An <i>Essay</i> on Milton	- T. B. Macaulay
✚	<i>Essay</i> on the Tragedies of Shakespeare	- Charles Lamb

✚ <i>Essays on Life, Art & Science</i>	- S. Butler (Victorian)
✚ <i>Essay on the Theatre</i>	- Oliver Goldsmith
✚ <i>Essay on the Human Understanding</i>	- John Locke
✚ <i>The Essay on Dramatic Poesy</i>	- John Dryden
✚ <i>Essay on the Development of Christian Doctrine</i>	- J. H. Newman
✚ <i>Essays on the Principles of Human Action</i>	- William Hazlitt
✚ <i>Farewell to Essay Writing</i>	- W. Hazlitt
✚ <i>The Complaint unto Pity</i>	- G. Chaucer
✚ <i>The Complaint of Mars</i>	- G. Chaucer
✚ <i>The Complaint to the King</i>	- Sir David Lyndsay
✚ <i>A Bachelor's Complaint to the Behaviour of Married People</i>	- Charles Lamb & Mary Lamb
✚ <i>The Complaint of Our Lady</i>	- Thomas Occleve
✚ <i>Occleve's Complaint</i>	- Thomas Occleve
✚ <i>The Wife's or Maiden's Complaint</i>	- J. J. Osborne
✚ <i>The Complaint of a Forsaken Indian Woman</i>	- William Wordsworth
✚ <i>The Complaint or Night Thoughts on Life</i>	- Edward Young
✚ <i>Spring & Fall</i>	- G. M. Hopkins
✚ <i>Caesar's Fall</i>	- John Webster & Dekker
✚ <i>The Fallen Idol</i>	- Graham Greene
✚ <i>Fallen Angels</i>	- Sir Noel Coward
✚ <i>Falles of Princess</i>	- John Lydgate
✚ <i>The History of the Decline & Fall of the Roman Empire</i>	- E. Gibbon
✚ <i>Decline & Fall</i>	- Evelyn Waugh
✚ <i>Rumour at Nightfall</i>	- Graham Greene
✚ <i>Free Fall</i>	- William Golding
✚ <i>All that Fall</i>	- Samuel Beckett
✚ <i>Things Fall Apart</i>	- Chinua Achebe
✚ <i>After the Fall</i>	- Arthur Miller
✚ <i>Confessions</i>	- J. J. Rousseau
✚ <i>A Last Confession</i>	- D. G. Rossetti
✚ <i>Confessio Amantis</i>	- John Gower

✚ The <i>Private</i> Papers of Henry Ryecroft	- George Gissing
✚ <i>Private</i> Life of an Indian Prince	- M. R. Anand
✚ The <i>Private</i> Memoirs & <i>Confessions</i> of a Justified Sinner	- James Hogg
✚ Supposed <i>Confessions</i> of a Second-Rate Sensitive Mind	- A. L. Tennyson
✚ The <i>Confessions</i> of an English Opium-Eater	- T. D. Quincey
✚ <i>Confession</i> of a Lover	- M. R. Anand
✚ The <i>Confessions</i> of a Drunkard	- Charles Lamb
✚ <i>Confessions</i> of a Young Man	- George Moore
✚ <i>Confessions</i> of an Inquiry Spirit	- S. T. Coleridge
✚ The <i>Confessions</i> of Harry Lorrequar	- Charles Lever
✚ <i>Confession</i> of 2000 Pages By	- M. R. Anand
✚ The <i>Shadow</i> Line : A Confession	- Joseph Conrad
✚ The <i>Shadow</i> Lines	- Amitabh Ghosh
✚ <i>Shadow</i> from Ladakh	- Bhabhani Bhattacharya
✚ In the <i>Shadow</i> of Pines	- Mandeep Rai
✚ The <i>Shadowy</i> Waters	- W. B. Yeats
✚ The <i>Fortunes & Misfortunes</i> of the Famous Moll Flanders	- Daniel Defoe
✚ The <i>Fortunate</i> Mistress	- Daniel Defoe
✚ The <i>Unfortunate</i> Traveller	- Thomas Nashe
✚ The <i>Fortunes</i> of Nigel	- Sir Walter Scott
✚ The <i>Fortunes</i> of Glencore	- Charles Lever
✚ The <i>Misfortunes</i> of Elphin	- T. L. Peacock
✚ The Old Man & the Sea @ A <i>Triumph</i> by Critics Hemingway	- Ernest
✚ The <i>Triumph</i> of the Machine	- D. H. Lawrence
✚ Comus @ The <i>Triumph</i> of Virtue	- John Milton
✚ The <i>Triumph</i> of Life	- Shelley
✚ The <i>Triumph</i> of Time	- A. C. Swinburne
✚ <i>Triumphant</i>	- John Dryden
✚ <i>Triumphal</i> March	- T. S. Eliot
✚ <i>Little</i> Gidding	- T. S. Eliot
✚ <i>Little</i> Nugget	- P. G. Wodehouse

✚ The <i>Little Dream</i>	- John Galsworthy
✚ The <i>Little Man</i>	- John Galsworthy
✚ <i>Little Dorrit</i>	- Charles Dickens
✚ The <i>Little Angel</i>	- G. K. Chesterton
✚ The <i>Little Minister</i>	- J. M. Barrie
✚ The <i>Little Gram-Shop</i>	- Raja Rao
✚ The <i>Little Review</i>	- Daniel Defoe
✚ The <i>Children</i> of Violence	- Dorris Lessing
✚ The Lost <i>Child</i> & Other Stories	- M. R. Anand
✚ Midnight's <i>Children</i>	- Salman Rushdie
✚ Dream <i>Children</i> : A Reverie	- Charles Lamb
✚ A <i>Child's</i> Laughter	- A. C. Swinburne
✚ A <i>Child's</i> Sleep	-A. C. Swinburne
✚ A <i>Child's</i> Garden of Verses	- R. L. Stevenson
✚ A <i>Child's</i> History of England	- Charles Dickens
✚ <i>Child</i> of Misfortune	- C. D. Lewis
✚ The Cry of the <i>Children</i>	- E. B. Browning
✚ On a Dead <i>Child</i>	- Robert Bridges
✚ The Water <i>Babies</i>	- Charles Kingsley
✚ The Duke's <i>Children</i>	- Anthony Trollope
✚ Among the School <i>Children</i>	- W. B. Yeats
✚ <i>Child</i> Who Never Grew	- Pearl S. Buck
✚ <i>Child</i> Harold's Pilgrimage	- G. Byron
✚ A Modest Proposal for Preventing the <i>Children</i> of Poor People from Being a Burden to Their Parents	- Jonathan Swift
✚ The <i>Sisters</i>	- A. C. Swinburne
✚ <i>Sister</i> Songs	- Francis Thompson
✚ My <i>Sister's</i> Sleep	- D. G. Rossetti
✚ <i>Sister</i> Helen	- D. G. Rossetti
✚ <i>Sister</i> Theresa	- George Moore
✚ My <i>Son's</i> <i>Father</i>	- Dom Moraes
✚ <i>Father</i> & <i>Son</i>	- Edmund Goose

✚ <i>Father and Sons</i>	- Ivan Turgenev
✚ <i>Dombey & Son</i>	- Charles Dickens
✚ <i>Sons & Lovers</i>	- D. H. Lawrence
✚ <i>Sons & Soldiers</i>	- Irwin Shaw
✚ Power & Glory	- Graham Greene
✚ <i>Power & Pity</i>	- M. R. Anand
✚ <i>The Provoked Wife</i>	- John Vanbrugh
✚ <i>The Country Wife</i>	- W. Wycherley
✚ Tender Husband	- Richard Steele
✚ <i>Provoked Husband</i>	- Vanbrugh & Colley Cibber
✚ <i>An Ideal Husband</i>	- Oscar Wilde
✚ <i>The Constant Couple</i>	- George Farquhar
✚ <i>The Constant Wife</i>	- W. S. Maugham
✚ <i>The Inconstant</i>	- G. Farquhar
✚ <i>The Constant Lover</i>	- Sir Richard Steele
✚ <i>Men & Women</i>	- A. L. Tennyson
✚ <i>Men, Women & Books</i>	- Leigh Hunt
✚ <i>Familiar Studies of Men & Books</i>	- R. L. Stevenson
✚ <i>The Superannuated Man</i>	- Charles Lamb
✚ <i>Autobiography of a Super Tramp</i>	- W. H. Davies
✚ <i>Supers & Superman</i>	- Phillip Guedalla
✚ The Invisible Man	- H. G. Wells
✚ <i>Invisible Man</i>	- Ralph Ellison
✚ Man who had <i>All the Luck</i>	- Arthur Miller
✚ <i>The Last Man</i>	- M. G. Shelley
✚ <i>The Hollow Men</i>	- T. S. Eliot
✚ <i>A Single Man</i>	- C. Isherwood
✚ <i>The Descent of Man</i>	- C. R. Darwin
✚ <i>The Middleman</i>	- H. A. Jones
✚ <i>The Mimic Men</i>	- V. S. Naipaul
✚ <i>Man of the People</i>	- Chinua Achebe
✚ <i>The Gentleman, Dancing Master</i>	- W. Wycherley

✚ The <i>Good-Natured Man</i>	- Oliver Goldsmith
✚ The Spirit of <i>Man</i>	- Robert Bridges
✚ <i>Dangling Man</i>	- Saul Bellow
✚ Our <i>Man</i> in Havana	- Graham Greene
✚ The <i>Man</i> Who Was <i>Thursday</i>	- G. K. Chesterton
✚ The Poor <i>Man & Lady</i>	- Thomas Hardy
✚ <i>Women</i> in <i>Love</i>	- D. H. Lawrence
✚ <i>Love's</i> Cross- Currents	- A. C. Swinburne
✚ <i>Tyrannic Love</i>	- John Dryden
✚ The Growth of <i>Love</i>	- Robert Bridges
✚ <i>Love</i> Disdained	- Thomas Watson
✚ <i>Love's</i> Last Shift	- Colley Cibber
✚ I Never Shall <i>Love</i> the <i>Snow</i> Again	- Robert Bridges
✚ <i>Lying Lover</i>	-R. Steele
✚ <i>Lady Chatterley's Lover</i>	- D .H. Lawrence
✚ <i>Sylvia's Lovers</i>	-E. C. Gaskell
✚ The Conscious <i>Lovers</i>	- R. Steele
✚ <i>Unconscious</i> Memory	- Samuel Butler (Victorian)
✚ The Fashionable <i>Lover</i>	- Richard Cumberland
✚ <i>Well Beloved</i>	-Thomas Hardy
✚ The <i>Man of Feeling</i>	- Henry Mackenzie @ <i>Addison of the North</i>
✚ <i>That Uncertain Feeling</i>	- Kingsley Amis
✚ <i>Men</i> Are from <i>Mars & Women</i> Are from <i>Venus</i>	- John Grey
✚ <i>Human</i> Knowledge	- Bertrand Russell
✚ <i>Human</i> Factor	- Graham Greene
✚ The <i>Man</i> of <i>Property</i>	- John Galsworthy
✚ Real <i>Property</i>	- Harold Monro
✚ The Good Companion	- J. B. Priestley
✚ <i>Companion</i>	-V. S.Naipaul
✚ <i>Good</i> Earth	- Pearl S. Buck
✚ <i>Ideas</i> of Good & Evil	- W. B. Yeats
✚ Of Goods & <i>Olives</i>	- Prithvi Nandy

✚ A <i>Good Time</i> was had by <i>All</i>	- Steve Smith
✚ <i>Good Thoughts</i> in <i>Bad Times</i>	- Thomas Fuller
✚ The <i>Lives</i> of the Poets	- Dr. Johnson
✚ <i>Lives</i> of the Novelists	- Sir Walter Scott
✚ The <i>Old Lady</i> Says 'No'	- Denis Johnston
✚ <i>Old Lady</i> Shows Her Medals	- Sir J. M. Barie
✚ <i>Lady</i> with the <i>Lapdog</i>	- Anton Chekhov
✚ The <i>Lady</i> with the Lamp	- Reginald Berkley
✚ <i>Lady</i> of the <i>Lake</i>	- Sir Walter Scott
✚ The <i>Lake</i> Isle of Innisfree	-W. B. Yeats
✚ The <i>Lake</i> of <i>Palms</i>	- R. C. Dutt
✚ The <i>Lady</i> is not for Burning	- Christopher Fry
✚ The <i>Lady</i> of <i>Shallot</i>	- A. L. Tennyson
✚ <i>Lady</i> <i>Windermere's</i> Fan	- Oscar Wilde
✚ The History of a Young <i>Lady</i>	- S. Richardson
✚ The <i>Magnetic Lady</i>	- Ben Jonson
✚ The <i>Scornful Lady</i>	- F. Beaumont & Fletcher
✚ My <i>Lady</i> <i>Ludlow</i>	- E. C. Gaskell
✚ The <i>Legend</i> of Good <i>Women</i>	- G. Chaucer
✚ A <i>Legend</i> of <i>Montrose</i>	- Sir Walter Scott
✚ A <i>Pure Woman</i>	- Thomas Hardy
✚ A <i>Woman</i> Young & Old	- W. B. Yeats
✚ The <i>Woman</i> on Platform 8	- Ruskin Bond
✚ <i>Women Beware Women</i>	- Thomas Middleton
✚ A <i>Woman</i> of No <i>Importance</i>	- Oscar Wilde
✚ <i>Importance</i> of Being Earnest	- Oscar Wilde
✚ Certain People of <i>Importance</i>	- A. G. Gardiner
✚ The <i>Duchess</i> of <i>Dadna</i>	- Oscar Wilde
✚ The <i>Duchess</i> Of <i>Padua</i>	-Oscar Wilde
✚ The <i>Duchess</i> of <i>Malfi</i>	- John Webster
✚ To the <i>Lady Margaret</i> <i>Ley</i>	- John Milton
✚ The Affliction of <i>Margaret</i>	- W. Wordsworth

✚ Old Blind <i>Margaret</i>	- Charles Lamb
✚ The Trials of <i>Margaret</i> Lyndsay	- John Wilson
✚ My Aunt <i>Margaret's</i> Mirror	- Sir Walter Scott
✚ Four <i>Portraits</i>	- Peter Quennell
✚ Contemporary <i>Portraits</i>	- William Hazlitt
✚ Imaginary <i>Portraits</i>	- W. H. Pater
✚ The <i>Portrait</i> of a Lady	- Khushwant Singh
✚ The <i>Portrait</i> of a Lady	- T. S. Eliot
✚ The <i>Portrait</i> of a Lady	- Henry James
✚ A <i>Portrait</i> of the Artist as a Young Man	- James Joyce
✚ The <i>Portrait</i> of Sporus	- Alexander Pope
✚ <i>Portrait</i> of India	- Ved Mehta
✚ <i>Portrait</i> of a Man with Red Hair	- Hugh Walpole
✚ <i>Portrait</i> of the Artist as a Young Dog	- D. M. Thomas
✚ Poetical <i>Sketches</i>	- William Blake
✚ Descriptive <i>Sketches</i>	- William Wordsworth
✚ An <i>Apology</i> for Idlers	- R. L. Stevenson
✚ <i>Apology</i> for Poetry	- Sir Philip Sidney
✚ <i>Apologia</i> Pro Vita Sua	- Newman
✚ The <i>Fugitive</i> & other Poems	- R. N. Tagore
✚ The <i>Fugitive</i>	- John Galsworthy
✚ <i>Mr. Bennett & Mrs. Brown</i>	- Virginia Woolf
✚ <i>Mrs. Battle's</i> Opinions on Whist	- Charles Lamb
✚ <i>Mr. Bristling</i> See it Through	- H. G. Wells
✚ <i>Mrs. Craddock</i>	- W. S. Maugham
✚ <i>Mrs. Danes</i> Defence	- H. A. Jones
✚ <i>Mrs. Dalloway</i>	- Virginia Woolf
✚ <i>Mr. H.</i>	- Charles Lamb
✚ <i>Mr. Noon</i>	- D. H. Lawrence
✚ <i>Mr. Norris</i> Changes Trains	- C. Isherwood
✚ The History of <i>Mr. Polly</i>	- H. G. Wells
✚ <i>Mr. Appolinax</i>	- T. S. Eliot

✚ <i>Mr. Perrin & Mr. Trail</i>	- Hugh Walpole
✚ <i>Mr. Sampath- The Printer of Malgudi</i>	- R. K. Narayan
✚ <i>Anatomy of Melancholy</i>	- Robert Burton
✚ <i>The Philosophy of Melancholy</i>	- T. L. Peacock
✚ <i>The Lover's Melancholy</i>	- John Ford
✚ <i>Ode to Melancholy</i>	- Thoams Hood
✚ <i>Ode to Melancholy</i>	- John Keats
✚ <i>Ode to Dejection</i>	- S. T. Coleridge
✚ <i>Stanzas Written in Dejection Near Naples, Ode to Naples</i>	- P. B. Shelley
✚ <i>Monuments of Honour</i>	- John Webster
✚ <i>A Man of Honour</i>	- W. S. Maugham
✚ <i>The Songs of Honour</i>	- Ralph Hodgson
✚ <i>The Maid of Honour</i>	- Philip Massinger
✚ <i>Sword of Honour</i>	- Evelyn Waugh
✚ <i>The Roots of Honour</i>	- John Ruskin
✚ <i>Roots</i>	- Arnold Wesker
✚ <i>Roots & Flowers</i>	- M. R. Anand
✚ <i>The Roots of the Mountains</i>	- William Morris
✚ <i>The Magic Mountain</i>	- Thomas Mann
✚ <i>Magic Mountain</i>	- M. Ved Vyas
✚ <i>The Magnetic Mountain</i>	- C. Day Lewis
✚ <i>The Loneliest Mountain</i>	- W. H. Davies
✚ <i>Daughters of a Mountain</i>	- Raja Rao
✚ <i>The Magician</i>	- W. S. Maugham
✚ <i>The Magicians</i>	- J. B. Priestley
✚ <i>The Magic Fishbone</i>	- Charles Dickens
✚ <i>The Song of the Sword</i>	- E. Henley
✚ <i>The Sword & the Sickle</i>	- M.R.Anand
✚ <i>The Song of the Shirt</i>	- Thomas Hood
✚ <i>Song of Solomon</i>	- Toni Morrison
✚ <i>The Song of the Pixies</i>	- S. T. Coleridge

✚ <i>Song of the French History</i>	- George Meredith
✚ <i>The Song of India</i>	- Sarojini Naidu
✚ <i>Irish Melodies</i>	- Thomas Moore
✚ <i>Hebrew Melodies</i>	- Lord Byron
✚ <i>A View from the Bridge</i>	- Arthur Miller
✚ <i>The Hindu View of Art</i>	- M. R. Anand
✚ <i>The Hindu View of Life</i>	- S . Radhakrishnan
✚ <i>An Idealist View of Life</i>	- S. Radhakrishnan
✚ <i>View from the U.N.</i>	- U. Thant
✚ <i>A Short View of the Profaneness & Immortality of the English Stage</i>	- Jeremy Collier
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✚ <i>The Vision of America</i>	- Allen Ginsberg
✚ <i>A Vision of Beasts & Gods</i>	- George Barker
✚ <i>The Visions of the Daughters of Albion</i>	- William Blake
✚ <i>The Vision of Judgement</i>	- Lord Byron
✚ <i>A Vision of Judgement</i>	- Robert Southey
✚ <i>The Vision of Sudden Death</i>	- Thomas De Quincey
✚ <i>Prometheus Unbound</i>	- P. B. Shelley
✚ <i>Prometheus Bound</i>	- E. B. Browning
✚ <i>Prometheus Rebound</i>	- B. S. Mardeskar
✚ <i>Prometheus, the Firegiver</i>	- Robert Bridges
✚ <i>Prometheus</i>	- Edwin Muir
✚ <i>Modern Prometheus, or Frankenstein</i>	- Mary Shelley
✚ <i>Adam Blair</i>	- J. G. Lockhart
✚ <i>Adam Bede</i>	- George Eliot
✚ <i>Amos Barton</i>	- George Eliot
✚ <i>Philaster</i>	- F. Beaumont & J. Fletcher
✚ <i>Alastor</i>	- P. B. Shelley
✚ <i>Mary Barton</i>	- E. C. Gaskell
✚ <i>Barry Lyndon</i>	- W. M. Thackeray
✚ <i>Evan Harrington</i>	- George Meredith
✚ <i>Ashenden</i>	- W. S. Maugham

✚ Common Asphodel	- Robert Graves
✚ Cato	- Addison
✚ Catalina	- W. S. Maugham
✚ Cataline	- Ben Jonson
✚ Catriona	- R. L. Stevenson
✚ Calista	- J. H. Newman
✚ The Cenci	P. B. Shelley
✚ Confederacy	- John Vanbrugh
✚ Conflagration	- Kamla Das
✚ The Profligate	- A. W. Pinero
✚ The <i>Rescue</i>	- Joseph Conrad
✚ The <i>Insurrection</i>	- W. H. Ainsworth
✚ The <i>Resurrection</i>	- W. B. Yeats
✚ Resurrection	- Leo Tolstoy
✚ Comfort of the <i>Resurrection</i>	- G. M. Hopkins
✚ Reincarnation	- Annie Besant
✚ Endimion	- John Lyly
✚ Endymion	- John Keats
✚ Persuasion	- Jane Austen
✚ Possession	- Kamala Markandaya
✚ My <i>Relations</i>	- Charles Lamb
✚ Poor <i>Relations</i>	- Charles Lamb
✚ Relations	- A. K. Ramanujan
✚ Relationship	- Jayant Mahapatra
✚ The <i>Keepsake</i>	- M. G. Shelley
✚ The <i>Namesake</i>	- Jhumpa Lahiri
✚ The <i>Trotternama</i>	- Irwin Allan Sealy
✚ No <i>Name</i>	- Wilkie Collins
✚ <i>Chance</i>	- Joseph Conrad
✚ In <i>Chancery</i>	- John Galsworthy
✚ Rhoda <i>Fleming</i>	- George Meredith
✚ Contarini <i>Fleming</i>	- Benjamin Disraeli

✚ <i>Deirdre</i>	- W. B. Yeats
✚ <i>Deirdre of Sorrow</i>	- J. M. Synge
✚ <i>Disgrace</i>	- J. M. Coetzee
✚ <i>Morte De Arthur (1470)</i>	- Sir Thomas Malory
✚ <i>Morte D' Arthur (1842)</i>	- A. L. Tennyson
✚ <i>Don Quixote</i>	- Miguel De Cervantes
✚ <i>Don Juan</i>	- Lord Byron
✚ <i>Don Carlos</i>	- Thomas Otway
✚ <i>Don Sebastian</i>	- John Dryden
✚ <i>De Profandis</i>	- Oscar Wilde
✚ <i>Susperia De Profundis</i>	- T. D. Quincey
✚ <i>Denis Duval</i>	- W. M. Thackeray
✚ <i>Departmental</i>	- R. L. Frost
✚ <i>Departmental Ditties</i>	- Rudyard Kipling
✚ <i>The Tin Drum</i>	- Gunter Grass
✚ <i>The Coffe Dams</i>	- Kamala Markandaya
✚ <i>Drum Taps</i>	- Walt Whitman
✚ <i>Distant Drums</i>	- Manohar Malgaonkar
✚ <i>The Dynasts</i>	- Thomas Hardy
✚ <i>Drake</i>	- Prof. Alfred Noyes
✚ <i>Dandy Dick</i>	- A. W. Pinero
✚ <i>Moby Dick</i>	- Herman Melville
✚ <i>The Devil's Disciple</i>	- G. B. Shaw
✚ <i>Mrs. Danes Defence</i>	- H. A. Jones
✚ <i>Difficult Daughters</i>	- Manju Kapoor
✚ <i>Daughters of a Mountain</i>	- Raja Rao
✚ <i>The Surgeon's Daughter</i>	- Sir Walter Scott
✚ <i>A Prayer for My Daughter</i>	- W. B. Yeats
✚ <i>The Visions of the Daughters of Albion</i>	- William Blake
✚ <i>Wives & Daughters</i>	- E. C. Gaskell
✚ <i>Advice to a Daughter</i>	- Lord Halifax
✚ <i>The Dark Dancer</i>	- Balchandra Rajam

✚ The <i>Dark Room</i>	- R. K. Narayan
✚ The <i>Light & the Dark</i>	- Sir C. P. Snow
✚ The <i>Dark is Light Enough</i>	- Christopher Fry
✚ The <i>Falcon</i>	- A. L. Tennyson
✚ <i>Façade</i>	- Edith Sitwell
✚ <i>Felix Randal</i>	- G. M. Hopkins
✚ <i>Felix Holt</i>	- George Eliot
✚ <i>Praeterita</i>	- John Ruskin
✚ <i>Henrietta Temple</i>	- Benjamin Disraeli
✚ <i>Importune</i>	- Shirley
✚ <i>Incognita</i>	- W. Congreve
✚ The <i>Inconstant</i>	- G. Farquhar
✚ <i>Irene</i>	- Dr. Johnson
✚ <i>Joan of Arc</i>	- Robert Southey
✚ <i>Joan of Arc</i>	- T. D. Quincey
✚ <i>Jill</i>	- Philip Larkin
✚ <i>Don Juan</i>	- Byron
✚ <i>Kim</i>	- Rudyard Kipling
✚ <i>Lucky Jim</i>	- Kingsley Amis
✚ <i>Lord Jim</i>	- Joseph Conrad
✚ <i>Lodore</i>	- Robert Southey
✚ <i>Ladore</i>	- M. G. Shelley
✚ <i>Laodicean or The Castle of the De Stanceys</i>	- Thomas Hardy
✚ <i>Laodamia</i>	- William Wordsworth
✚ <i>Lamia</i>	- John Keats
✚ <i>Lavengro</i>	- George Barrow
✚ <i>Lara</i>	- Lord Byron
✚ <i>Lear</i>	- Edward Bond
✚ <i>Lepanto</i>	- G. K. Chesterton
✚ <i>Lewti</i>	- S. T. Coleridge
✚ <i>Lenore</i>	- Walter Scott
✚ <i>Leonora</i>	- Maria Edgeworth

✚ Lipika	- R. N. Tagore
✚ Luria	- Robert Browning
✚ Luther	- J. J. Osborne
✚ Lupercal	-Ted Hughes
✚ Marius	-W. H . Pater
✚ Maurice	- E. M. Forster
✚ Maud	- A. L.Tennyson
✚ Marionettes	- W. Faulkner
✚ Merope	- M. Arnold
✚ Murphy	- Samuel Beckett
✚ Pericles & Aspasia	- W. S. Landor
✚ Pericles	- W. Shakespeare
✚ Retaliation	- Oliver Goldsmith
✚ Reluctance	- R. L. Frost
✚ Reluctant Guru	- R. K. Narayan
✚ The Rainbow	- W. Wordsworth
✚ The Rainbow	- D. H. Lawrence
✚ <i>The Rainbow</i>	- Pearl S. Buck
✚ <i>Solomon</i>	- Matthew Prior
✚ Salome	- Oscar Wilde
✚ Sanctuary	- W. Faulkner
✚ Sartoris	- William Faulkner
✚ The Spire	- William Golding
✚ Scoop	- Evelyn Waugh
✚ Samson <i>Agoniste</i>	- John Milton
✚ <i>Sweeney Agonistes</i>	- T. S. Eliot
✚ Noble <i>Essence</i>	-Osbert Sitwell
✚ <i>Ape & Essence</i>	- Aldous Huxley
✚ <i>Venus</i> Observed	- Christopher Fry
✚ <i>Venice</i> Preserved	-Thomas Otway
✚ <i>Black Venus</i>	- Angela Carter
✚ <i>Venus & Adonais</i>	- William Shakespeare

✚ <i>Adonais</i>	- P. B. Shelley
✚ <i>Grongar Hill</i>	- John Dyer
✚ <i>Gryll Grange</i>	- Thomas L. Peacock
✚ <i>The Holy Grail</i>	- A. L. Tennyson
✚ <i>Villa Rubein</i>	- John Galsworthy
✚ <i>Villette</i>	- Charlotte Bronte
✚ <i>The Vivisector</i>	- Patrick White
✚ <i>Voss</i>	- Patrick White
✚ <i>Vittoria</i>	- George Meredith
✚ <i>Virginians</i>	- W. M. Thackeray
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✚ <i>Exiled</i>	- John Galsworthy
✚ <i>Exile</i>	- James Joyce
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✚ <i>The Plain Dealer</i>	- W. Wycherley
✚ <i>The Double Dealer</i>	- William Congreve
✚ <i>The Earth for Sale</i>	- Harold Monro
✚ <i>The Secret Life</i>	- H. G. Barker
✚ <i>The Secret Agent</i>	- Joseph Conrad
✚ <i>The Confidential Agent</i>	- Graham Greene
✚ <i>The Confidential Clerk</i>	- T. S. Eliot
✚ <i>Loss & Gain</i>	- J. H. Newman
✚ <i>Limits & Renewals</i>	- Rudyard Kipling
✚ <i>The Less Deceived</i>	- Philip Larkin
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✚ <i>London Merchant</i>	- George Lillo
✚ <i>The Merchant of Venice</i>	- W. Shakespeare
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✚ The <i>Pleasures of Ignorance</i>	- Robert Lynd
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✚ <i>A Defence</i> of Poetry	- P. B. Shelley
✚ <i>Defence</i> of Guenevere	- William Morris
✚ <i>Mrs. Danes Defence</i>	- H. A. Jones
✚ <i>Prelude</i> to Adventure	- Hugh Walpole
✚ <i>A Prelude</i>	- D. H. Lawrence
✚ The <i>Prelude</i>	- William Wordsworth
✚ The <i>Holy War & Profane State</i>	-Thomas Fuller
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✚ The <i>Loved One</i>	- Evelyn Waugh
✚ The <i>Kindly Ones</i>	- Anthony Powell
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✚ Red Roses <i>for Me</i>	- Sean O'casey
✚ The Man <i>Within</i>	- Graham Greene
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✚ The Hot <i>Gates</i>	- William Golding
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✚ <i>Roderick</i> Hudson	- Henry James
✚ <i>Roderick</i>	- Robert Southey
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✚ The <i>Naturalist</i> in La Plata	- W. H. Hudson
✚ <i>Death</i> in the <i>Castle</i>	- Pearl S. Buck

✚ <i>Death in the Afternoon</i>	- Ernest Hemingway
✚ <i>Death in Venice</i>	- Thomas Mann
✚ <i>Death of the Author</i>	- Roland Barthes
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✚ <i>The Death of Coleridge</i>	- C. Lamb
✚ <i>Death on the Nile</i>	- Agatha Christie
✚ <i>Death under Sail</i>	- C. P. Snow
✚ <i>Death & After</i>	- Annie Besant
✚ <i>Death Be Not Proud</i>	- J. Gunther
✚ <i>Overtures to Death</i>	- C. Day Lewis
✚ <i>Death & Entrances</i>	- D. M. Thomas
✚ <i>Chronicle of a Death Foretold</i>	- G. G. Marquez
✚ <i>Dialogue with Death</i>	- Arthur Koestler
✚ <i>A Night Piece on Death</i>	- Thomas Parnell
✚ <i>Death & Immortality</i>	- Edward Young
✚ <i>The Life & Death of Jason</i>	- William Morris
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✚ <i>The Anti- Death League</i>	- Kingsley Amis
✚ <i>The Death Bed</i>	- Thomas Hood
✚ <i>Balder Dead</i>	- Matthew Arnold
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✚ <i>Eros & Psyche</i>	- Robert Bridges
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✚ My Enemy's <i>Enemy</i>	- Kingsley Amis
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✚ Troilus & Cryseyde	- G. Chaucer
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✚ <i>Troilus & Cressida</i>	- William Shakespeare
✚ The Preface or Epilogue to <i>Troilus & Cressida</i>	- John Dryden
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✚ <i>Officers & Gentleman</i>	- Evelyn Waugh
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✚ The <i>Lord of the Isle</i>	- Sir Walter Scott
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✚ <i>Lord of the Flies</i>	- William Golding

✚ <i>Queen</i> Anelida	- G. Chaucer
✚ <i>Queen</i> Mab	- P. B. Shelley
✚ <i>Queen</i> Mary	- A. L. Tennyson
✚ The <i>Queen</i> of Carthage	- C. Marlowe, Nashe & Marston
✚ The Indian <i>Queen</i>	- Roger Boyle
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✚ <i>Hymn</i> to Apollo	- P. B. Shelley
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✚ <i>Masque</i> of Blackness	- Ben Jonson
✚ <i>Masque</i> of Beauty	- Ben Jonson
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✚ Evelyn's <i>Innes</i>	- George Moore
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✚ <i>Finningan's</i> Wake	- James Joyce
✚ The <i>Castle</i> of Otranto	- Horace Walpole
✚ The <i>Castle</i> of <i>Indolence</i>	- James Thomso
✚ Ode to <i>Indolence</i>	- John Keats
✚ Windsor <i>Castle</i>	- W. H. Ainsworth
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✚ The Isle of <i>Palms</i>	- John Wilson of Ellery @ Christopher North
✚ The <i>Wild Palms</i>	- W. Faulkner
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✚ Susperia <i>De</i> Profundis	- T. D. Quincey
✚ Amours <i>De</i> Voyage	- A. H. Clough
✚ Goston <i>De</i> Labour	- W. H. Pater
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✚ <i>Between</i> the Lines	- Kuldeep Nayyar
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✚ <i>Between</i> the Acts	- Virginia Woolf

✚ <i>Between Tears & Laughter</i>	- M. R. Anand
✚ <i>Trench Without Tears</i>	- Sir Terrence Rattigan
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✚ The <i>Hounds of Spring</i>	- A. C. Swinburne
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✚ The Sand <i>Box</i>	- Edward Albee
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✚ The <i>Wreck</i>	- R. N. Tagore
✚ The <i>Wreck</i> of the Deutschland	- G. M. Hopkins
✚ <i>Caleb</i> Williams or Things as They are	- William Godwin
✚ <i>Coelebs</i> in Search of a Wife	- Hannah More
✚ <i>Cobwebs</i> in the Sun	- Shiv. K. Kumar
✚ The <i>House</i> of the <i>Cawebs</i>	- George Gissing
✚ A Chapter on <i>Dreams</i>	- R. L. Stevenson
✚ The <i>Dream</i> of John Bull	- William Morris
✚ The Little <i>Dream</i>	- John Galsworthy
✚ The Narrow <i>Corner</i>	- W. S. Maugham
✚ <i>Dangerous Corner</i>	- J. B. Priestley
✚ The <i>Dangerous</i> Summer	- Ernest Hemmingway
✚ <i>Dangerous</i> Play	- Andrew Motion
✚ Hereward the <i>Wake</i>	- Charles Kingsley
✚ Finningan's <i>Wake</i>	- James Joyce

✚ The Queen's Wake	- James Hogg
✚ Wake Up India	- Annie Besant
✚ The <i>Idea</i> of a Christian Society	- T. S. Eliot
✚ <i>Ideas</i> of Good & Evil	- W. B. Yeats
✚ The <i>Idea</i> of Comedy	- George Meredith
✚ The <i>Idea</i> of a University Defined	- J. H. Newman
✚ <i>Idea</i> of Christian Church	- W. G. Ward
✚ A Philosophical Inquiry into the Origin of Our <i>Ideas</i> of the Sublime & Beautiful	- Edmund Burke
✚ <i>Idea</i>	- Michael Drayton
✚ A <i>Bend</i> in the Ganges	- Manohar Malgaonkar
✚ A <i>Bend</i> in the River	- V. S. Naipaul
✚ <i>Seven Circles Round the Fire</i>	-Mahesh Dattani
✚ The <i>Circle</i>	- W. S. Maugham
✚ District & <i>Circle</i>	- Seamus Heaney
✚ First <i>Circle</i>	- A. Solzhenitsyn
✚ The Inner <i>Circle</i>	- Jonathan First
✚ The Circle of Reason	- Amitabh Ghosh
✚ Bermuda <i>Triangle</i>	- Charles Berlitz
✚ The Naked <i>Triangle</i>	- Bulwant Gargi
✚ The Still <i>Centre</i>	- Stephen Spender
✚ Finding the <i>Centre</i>	- V. S. Naipaul
✚ The <i>Palace of Art</i>	- A. L. Tennyson
✚ The <i>Glass Palace</i>	- Amitabh Ghose
✚ The <i>Hour-Glass</i>	- W. B. Yeats
✚ The <i>Hour of Magic</i>	- W. H. Davies
✚ In Evil <i>Hour</i>	- G. G. Marquez
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✚ A Looking <i>Glass</i> for London & England	- Green and Lodge
✚ The Burning <i>Glass</i> & other Poems	- Walter De La Mare
✚ The <i>Glass</i> Managere	- Tennessee William
✚ <i>Strange</i> Meeting	- Wilfred Owen

✚ After <i>Strange Gods</i>	- T. S. Eliot
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✚ The Razor's <i>Edge</i>	- W. S. Maugham
✚ Moments of <i>Being</i>	- Virginia Woolf
✚ The <i>Edge</i> of Sadness	- Edwin O'connor
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✚ The <i>Rape of the Lock</i>	- Alexander Pope
✚ The <i>Rape of the Lucrece</i>	- W. Shakespeare
✚ The <i>Rape</i> of Earth	- G. V. Jacques & R. O. White
✚ <i>Rape</i> - Bangladesh	- Anthony Mascarenhas
✚ The Widow of the <i>Bye</i> Street	- John Masefield
✚ <i>Bye-Bye</i> Blackbird	- Anita Desai
✚ <i>Goodbye</i> Columbus	- Philip Roth
✚ The <i>Goodbye</i> Party to Miss Pushpa, T. S.	- Nissim Ezekiel
✚ <i>Goodbye</i> to Elsa	- Saros Cowasjee

<i>Goodbye to Berlin</i>	- C. Isherwood
<i>Goodbye to all that</i>	- Robert Graves
<i>Thank You , Jeeves</i>	- P. G. Wodehouse
<i>Thank You, Fog : Last Poem</i>	- W. H. Auden

References:

1. Arora, Dr. Sudhir K. , "A Handbook of Language and Literature for Competitive Examinations-PGT/TGT", Prakash Book Depot, Bareilly, U.P., Reprint-2012, ISBN-978-81-7977-419-9
2. Daiches, David. A Critical History of English Literature. New Delhi: Allied Publishers Pvt. Limited, 1979; rpt. 2005.
3. Jain, Dr. B.B., " UGC NET/JRF/SET, English Paper-II", Upkar Prakashan, Agra-2, U.P., Pages-132, ISBN-978-81-7482-875-0, Code No.-940
4. Jain, Dr. B.B., " UGC NET/JRF/SET, English Paper-III", Upkar Prakashan, Agra-2, U.P., Pages-184, ISBN-978-81-7482-419-6, Code No.-1544
5. Kumar, Satish & Bansal, Anupama; " A History of English Literature- From the Age of Chaucer to the Age of Twentieth Century", Lakshmi Narain Agarwal, Agra, U.P., ISBN-81-85778-70-1
6. Mundra & Mundra, J.N.,S.C.; "A History of English Literature-Vol-I- Anglo-Saxon Period to the Age of Dryden", Prakash Book Depot, Bareilly, U.P., 2011, Pages 464, ISBN (Vol-I) -978-81-7977-251-5 , ISBN-Set-978-81-7977-254-6
7. Mundra & Mundra, J.N.,S.C.; "A History of English Literature-Vol-II- The Age of Pope to the Romantic Period ", Prakash Book Depot, Bareilly, U.P.,Reprint-2005, Pages 542, ISBN (Vol-II) -81-85897-38-7 , ISBN-Set-81-85897-36-0
8. Mundra & Mundra, J.N.,S.C.; "A History of English Literature- Vol-III- The Victorian Age to the Present Day ", Prakash Book Depot, Bareilly, U.P., Reprint-2004, Pages 730, ISBN-Set-81-85897-36-0
9. "Objective English" , Pratiyogita Sahitya Series, Sahitya Bhavan, Agra, U.P., Pages 290 , Code-953
10. Sachdeva, S.K., "Year Book ", Competition Success Review, New Delhi, 1998 , Pp 876, P.No.453-468

11. Tetarwal, C.R., "UGC-NET English Objective Solved Papers", Amar Ujala Publications Ltd., Noida, U.P., 2012, Pages 226
12. Verma, A.S., "UGC: NET/SLET English Paper-II", Pratiyogita Sahitya Series, Sahitya Bhavan, Agra, U.P., Code- A500

